

DEVELOPING THE AXIOLOGICAL POSITION OF FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS – AS AN IMPORTANT DIRECTION OF HISTORY EDUCATION

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During the years of independence, in order to educate a harmonious generation, the future of Uzbekistan, in the spirit of respect for the history of the Motherland, historical memory, historical appreciation, and historical pride, it was set a goal to raise the level of providing young people with knowledge about our great heritage, to develop the historical consciousness of young students in the education system at all levels. Today, the establishment of the Public Council on the latest history of Uzbekistan, increasing attention to increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, decisions on the establishment of international research centers studying the scientific work of great thinkers, as well as reforms in the field of education are aimed at raising a comprehensively mature, patriotic generation. In particular, understanding our national identity, studying the ancient and rich history of our Motherland, strengthening scientific research work in this regard, and comprehensive support for the activities of scientists in the humanitarian field are of great importance¹. Developing students' historical consciousness and studying its role in socio-spiritual life and the system of personal education is of theoretical and practical importance.

The Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan sets out the following tasks: further improving the system of continuing education, improving the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions, and educating young people who are independent thinkers, loyal to the Motherland, and have a firm life outlook². In this regard, it is important to clarify the axiological criteria and indicators for the development of professional competence in students of higher education institutions based on the system of professional values and motives for activity, to improve the organizational

structure and mechanisms for the development of the system of values, and to develop creative educational technologies.

It is known from history that the first axiological ideas have an ancient history, and their flourishing dates back to the territory of ancient Greece. For example, the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates always tried to find an answer to the question "What are interests?", - an example of our idea³. So, interest is undoubtedly one of the main topics of axiological theory.

In dictionaries created before the 80s of the 20th centuries, the category of axiology does not appear, on the contrary, the level of values is defined in a unique way, and it is noted that it is understood as a set of important elements of the inner psyche of a person, strengthened by life experience, and the whole set of experiences.

In particular, the process of building a new democratic society, which is consistently ongoing in our country, increases the relevance of the topic of values. Today, issues such as re-evaluating values, restoring ancient national values, preserving them and passing them on to future generations, identifying aspects of reforms and changes that are becoming new values in the minds of our people, and using methods appropriate to these values in solving existing problems have arisen. Solving them has begun to put axiological topics on the agenda. Currently, the subject of "Philosophy of Values" (Axiology) is being taught in a number of higher educational institutions of our country.

The urgent need for the development of modern higher education is the study of axiological problems, national and universal values, making the spiritual and social problems of the student one of the priority tasks. After all, values are considered a means of connecting the past and the future, and they, being mastered, recognized and manifested in the sphere of needs-emotions and subject-personal activity, have a direct impact on the deeper mastering of the professional sphere of the individual.

As is known, the formation of a sense of respect for national values in students is not only an expansion of the circle of knowledge (information), but also a strengthening of confidence in the future. American psychologist Abraham Maslow believes that in the "hierarchy of human needs", which is still present in many textbooks, the need for peace and security, the need for confidence in the future, comes after natural needs. Let's say that the art of architecture, which is part of the cultural heritage of the Uzbek people, has been created for thousands of years and is, as it were, a living expression of history for us. Because our

historical cultural monuments are not just structures that remind us of the distant past, but also an important tool that develops a person's sense of national pride, national pride, provides objective historical information about the past, enhances historical patriotism, and, in addition, is an expression of historical consciousness in the life of society, forming a historical culture. Improving sociological and pedagogical approaches in the implementation of the processes of forming and developing a positive attitude towards values in young people (especially students) is an important factor in social development.

It is important to study the laws and trends of changes in historical consciousness under the influence of globalization processes, to identify the positive and negative aspects of this influence. Today, at a time when ideological and ideological attacks are on the rise, historical consciousness creates immunity in a person against these attacks and forms the function of analyzing the socio-political and historical reasons for various historical claims. In addition, using methods that develop positive attitudes inherent in values, it also serves to form and develop in young people a sense of patriotism, pride in belonging to a particular nation and people, historical patriotism, the ability to feel identity with their nation, national pride, and national honor. These characteristics are considered the basis for the individual to mature as a patriot, thereby building a solid foundation for the country to ensure its stable future.

A lot of work is also being done in teaching history. It is known that through history, students are given information and examples about all aspects of politics, culture, art, economics, and social life, while studying and gaining knowledge about historical events of past periods. At the same time, students, along with mastering history, also increase their knowledge in works of fine art. Through works of fine art, they also gain an idea of the socio-political life of that period, the culture, and how developed the people were. The process of knowing history begins with the assimilation of historical facts. The peculiarity of historical facts is that they are never exactly repeated. At the same time, the knowledge of individual historical facts by students does not express the concept of having mastered history. If there is no logical connection between facts, then a simple set of facts will monotonize knowledge and prevent the conscious assimilation of historical materials. Thus, in the process of studying history, facts should not only be studied, but also compared, identified and to a certain extent systematized, ensuring the assimilation of the necessary connections between them.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the analysis of scientific literature on the problem under study confirms that the orientation of students to values is a product of their development as individuals, in which the formation, transformation and integration of potentials gradually leads to a higher integrity. In this process, the potential of students to be committed to scientific and national values plays an important role.

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